

TEACHERS' PRACTICES ON THE 21ST CENTURY SKILLS AND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN THE CORE SUBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the extent of practice of the Senior High School teachers on the 21st century skills to develop their students' competence and become globally competitive. The respondents of the study were the 348 students representing the first three batches of Senior High School graduates of Foundation Preparatory Academy. The researcher utilized the descriptive–correlational method, used a validated questionnaire, and employed mean, weighted mean, Chi-square and Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient. The students' grades in the core subjects were also considered. The study revealed that the extent of teachers' practices on the following 21st century skills is high: (a) Learning and Innovation Skills; (b) Information, Media, and Digital Literacy Skills, and (c) Life and Career Skills. It was also found out that the students' academic performance in the core subjects is generally in the outstanding level. Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between sex and students' overall academic performance in the core subjects in favor of the female students. A significant relationship also existed between the type of Junior High School completed from and the students' overall academic performance in the core subjects in favor of those coming from public high schools.

Keywords: *learning and innovation skills, media and digital literacy skills, life and career skill*

INTRODUCTION

In today's information age, education for sustainable development is given emphasis to hone every individual's ability to acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values which are important in shaping one's viable future. This requires a transformation of the educational system, from the traditional "teachers on-stage" scenario, to active, participative, and experiential classroom practices where learners are actively engaged and are proactive in making a difference in this globally competitive world. One of the most significant changes in the educational history of the Philippines is the implementation of the K to 12 Program. The major change brought about by this program is the addition of two (2) years in the secondary curriculum, known as Senior High School. It is assumed that the additional two (2) years is important to improve the mastery of basic competencies and to provide better preparation of the graduates for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, employment, and entrepreneurship (Presidential Communications Development and Strategic Planning Office, 2013).

According to Care, Kim, Vista, and Anderson (2018), with the implementation of the K-12 curriculum, there is a major shift in the educational learning goals for sustainable development. They further stated that developing young citizens to be globally competitive requires equipping them with the 21st century skills, such as: problem solving, collaborative, critical thinking skills; life and career skills; and information, media, and technology skills.

However, Lugtu (2018) reported that the first graduates of the K-12 program did not make the full cut as these graduates are still half-baked, unprepared, and incompetent. The Philippine Chamber of Commerce and Industry (PCCI) claimed that the K-12 graduates are not yet ready for work and that they lack the necessary 21st century skills such as "innovation" and "critical thinking skills". Moreover, according to the Global Competitiveness Index 2017–2018 released by the World Economic Forum, the Philippines ranked 76th for quality of Math and Science education. Meanwhile, on the basis of the overall Philippine Educational system, the country ranked poorly coming in at 113th out of 127 countries in the 2017 Global Innovation Index (The Global Competitiveness Report, 2017). In addition, the 2018 results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), which measures the ability of 15-year-old students to use their Reading, Mathematics, and Science knowledge and skills, disclosed that out of the 79 participating countries, the Philippines ranked second to the last in both Science and Mathematics (PISA Result, 2018).

The declining performance of our students, especially in the Philippine Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), evidently proves that there is still a problem in the curriculum. Cordon and Polong (2020) stressed that since PISA is a tool that measures not only the students' 21st century skills competency but also teachers' performance in teaching the students of the said skills, it is imperative that the curriculum and the educational system in general must be revised. It is strongly recommended that a review of the different aspects concerned be done — from the curriculum to the teachers' performance, including students' readiness in the examination which might contribute to students' low performance in Math and Science. It is on this note that the researcher found the urgency to conduct a study on teachers'

extent of practices of the 21st century skills and on how these practices influence the Senior High School graduates' academic performance as indicated in the average ratings in each of their core subjects to determine their level of competence of the 21st century skills. The researcher aims to use the results of the study as a basis in designing a program that will improve the Senior High School core subject curricula and instruction to help the educational system in the hope that the school could offer the students "world class education".

This section presents the related literature and studies relevant to the K to 12 Program; the 21st Century Skills such as Learning and Innovation Skills; Information, Media, and Literacy Skills; Life and Career Skills; the students' profile; and Issues and Challenges of the 21st Century Skills.

K-12 Curriculum. The advent of new technology paved the way for students to gain opportunities of becoming more technologically-adept and be exposed to varied learning modalities. With this development, today's new generation is exposed to the so-called "digital era" where modern technology such as smart phones, computers, laptops, iPads, and the internet are their primary means of acquiring information and knowledge.

In this context, schools and teachers play important roles in shaping students' learning in such a way that the quality and learning they acquire are aligned with the growing demands of the society and the job market. In the study of Rotherham and Willingham (as cited in the works of Magno, Bardemorilla, & Pecson, 2016), it is stated that business leaders, politicians, and educators unanimously expressed that students must be equipped with the necessary 21st century skills for them to be able to compete in the global market. In line with this urgent need, teachers must develop their learners' 21st century skills by providing students with authentic learning opportunities that will maximize their potentialities and capabilities, thus making them competent individuals endowed with the skills necessary to cope with the changes of time. In the Philippines, with the enactment of the K to 12 Program signed into law by former President Benigno Aquino III in accordance with the Basic Education Act of 2013 (R.A. 10533), the promotion of developing 21st century skills among Filipino learners to become functionally literate and holistically developed has been regulated. The law envisions to produce graduates that are ready to take on the challenges of today's generation and are motivated to navigate the increasingly globalized world. The K-12 curriculum in the Philippines is a basic education program which covers kindergarten education, 6 years of primary education, 4 years of junior high school, and 2 years of senior high school. Incoming Senior High School students are given the freedom to choose from the 4 tracks which include the Academic track; Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood track; Sports track; and Arts and Design track. The Academic track is composed of 4 strands which include Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM); Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM); Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS); and General Academic Strand (GAS). The Technical, Vocational, Livelihood (TVL) track also consists of Home Economics (HE); Information and Communication Technology (ICT); Agri-Fishery Arts (AFA); and Industrial Arts (IA) (DepEd, 2016). It was believed that the program will give enough time for the mastery of concepts and skills, equipping lifelong learners with the deemed abilities needed in the field of employment, entrepreneurship, skills development, and college education (Trance & Trance, 2019).

21st Century Skills. Education in the 21st century highlights globalization and internationalization which requires the command of the 21st century skills. The 21st century skills are lifelong learning competencies needed by students to strive in the future (Voogt & Roblin, 2010). Equipping students with 21st century skills plays the key role in preparing the 21st century learners to survive and excel in the new global environment (Apple, 2008). According to David Ross (2017), 21st century skills do not only provide students with the framework for successful learning, but it also equips them with the skills needed to survive in this very dynamic society where change is constant. He further added that these skills give children the opportunity to develop fundamental skills required for them to express themselves with reason, think creatively and critically, collaboratively work with others, and enable them to actively participate in a globally connected world. These skills and their integration in classroom instruction are the focus in the recent educational reforms as well as in curriculum development (Savu et al., 2014; Boholano, 2017). According to Donovan, Green, and Mason (2014), students who do not possess these skills could have difficulties in keeping up with the pace of the demands in the competitive work environment. Therefore, students have to gain more knowledge about different subject areas to lead a successful life, and at the same time, they have to achieve some crucial skills, which will help them survive in the fast-changing world (Rahman, 2019).

Different institutions and organizations classified the 21st century skills in various ways. The Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21), a joint government corporate organization, classifies competencies into 3 skill sets and 12 components. The first skill set is life and career skills that include flexibility and adaptability; initiative and self-direction; social and cross-cultural interaction; productivity and accountability; and leadership and responsibility. The second set is learning and innovation skills, such as critical thinking and problem solving; communication; collaboration; creativity; and innovation. The last set includes the digital literacy skills that encompass information; media literacy; and technology literacy (as cited in Shidiq & Yamtinah, 2019).

On the other hand, the international research project – Assessment and Teaching of 21st Century Skills (ATCS) – classifies the 21st century skills into the following 4 types: (1) ways of thinking (creativity and innovation; critical thinking, problem solving, and decision-making; learning to learn and metacognition); (2) ways of working (communication and collaboration); (3) tools for working (information and ICT literacy); and (4) living in the world (citizenship; life and career skills; personal and social responsibility) (Binkley et al., 2012).

According to the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development, the 21st century is the “knowledge economy” which puts emphasis on skills as its global currency needed in the future society (OECD, 2012). Ongardwanich, Kanjanawasee, and Tuipae (2015) stressed that the 21st century skills help every individual to learn and adapt to changes in the global economy which further serves as the key to shifting one’s economic status. In line with this, it is natural that significant reforms in the educational system must be made to cope with the intense transformation. These reforms must be focused in educating the so-called “generation Z” to become lifelong learners who are equipped with more knowledge, can effectively communicate and contribute to sustainable development, and can cope with the demands of the present century (Salas-Pilco, 2013).

Cheng (2017) observed that these educational reforms made use of the three principles of science learning which emphasized the following: students as active learners; learning is achieved through experience, hence experiential learning is required; and different students may achieve differently and should be allowed diverse learning paths and diverse learning outcomes. Students are given the opportunity to explore and manage their own learning while teachers only facilitate students to become active learners. This marks the shift in the educational system, from rote learning and memorization of facts to the development of the 21st century skills of creativity; critical thinking; communication; collaboration; information, media, and technological skills; and problem-solving skills (Urbani, Roshandel, Michaels, & Truesdell, 2017; Van Laar et al., 2017). They claimed that these skills are important in producing effective and efficient citizens who can competently participate in the “knowledge economy” of the future wherein human beings are called as the “highly qualified human capital”.

Learning and Innovation Skills. Creativity and innovation open the doors to a more productive, engaging, and meaningful experience in generating unique ideas and concepts. According to the Partnership for 21st Century Skills Framework, Learning and Innovation Skills are sets of skills which include the 4Cs, such as creativity and innovation, critical thinking and problem solving, communication, and collaboration skills. The Partnership for 21st century learning emphasized that students nowadays must be taught on how to acquire these skills to prepare themselves in this dynamic world where the demands for a result-oriented workforce are highly needed by the booming industries worldwide. In addition, the Common Core Standards also support PISA’s focus and expressed that all curricula, especially Mathematics, must prepare students the hallmarks of Innovation and Learning Skills which include communication, collaboration, and problem-solving skills through mathematical modeling for students to solve problems that they may encounter in everyday life (Common Core State Standards, 2010).

Maffia (2019) mentioned in his study that educational systems all over the world are promoting the development of the 21st century skills such as collaboration, communication, creativity, digital literacy, and self-directed learning. Anagun, Kilic, Atalay, and Yasar (2015) posited that for students to effectively deal with a more complex world in the 21st century, it is important that teachers and the school, in general, should prepare them for social and economic life by acquiring all these sub-skills of learning and innovation skills. In the study of Atalay and Boyaci (2019), they found that students will be able to develop and utilize creativity and innovation skills and will successfully develop the 4Cs, provided that they are given the proper facilitation process, materials, and genius hour during the course of the study using new technologies, and their creative imagination in creating products. The researchers noticed that a remarkable development on the students’ learning and innovation skills was observed in each stage of the “Slowmation Application” also termed as “Slow Animation”. This is an approach to teaching that utilized a multimodal digital representation, which is used to explain difficult concepts in bite-sized learning. In the planning, narrating, production, and reproduction stages, the students’ critical thinking and problem-solving skills were developed in the process as they effectively communicated and collaborated with others in the accomplishment of the given task.

Zulkifi and Hashim (2020) conducted a study on the application of philosophy emphasizing the use of 4C that aims to develop students' potential to make use of their mental acts, thinking, reasoning, and judgment especially when they are solving problems. It was found that the 4C in students is less developed because the connection between reading and thinking is not fully established for the reason that they lack the intellectual stimulation that could strengthen and enhance their existing literary experience. In line with this finding, he pointed out that teachers must be knowledgeable in preparing critical thinking stimuli, questions, discussions, and learning opportunities that would increase students' engagement and active participation to enhance their critical thinking skills. Sharp, Green, and Lewis (2018) also stressed that the students' power of inquiry and motivation to think critically can be ignited only if teachers strategically design intriguing learning experiences that focus on issues and events which are commonly encountered by students.

Putri and Prodjosantoso (2020) conducted a quasi-experimental research in discovering the effectiveness of guided inquiry-based natural science comic media in teaching natural science subjects. The finding of the study unveiled that students' critical thinking skills, scientific attitudes, and competence achievement greatly improved when teachers used natural science comic media. The researchers believed that the students' motivation and understanding can be best improved when teachers used learning media to help process the discussions in order to facilitate the students' understanding and improve their creativity and critical thinking skills. Researchers pointed out that in order to fully develop the learners' 21st century skills, different teaching strategies, such as guided inquiry-based natural science comic media, problem-solving, blended learning, inquiry-based learning and collaborative learning as well as personalized learning and reflective teaching, are necessary (Rahman, 2019; Tavares, 2012; Lipman, 2017; Zulkifii & Hachim, 2020).

Another sub-skill of learning and innovation skills which is deemed important in the fast-changing world is problem-solving skill. In the words of Rahman (2019), problem solving is one of the fundamental human cognitive processes which help an individual find a way in achieving his desired goals. Graessel et al. (as cited by Stadler, Herborn, Mustafic, & Greiff, 2020) expressed that collaborative problem solving requires learners to possess sufficient cognitive problem-solving and social collaboration skills. Problem solving is the most essential ability required by society and is also considered as an important component in developing students' critical thinking skills for them to be able to face and cope with the challenges of the "K-society" (Rahman, 2019). Newland (2016) also claimed the same when he said that in this so-called "knowledge economy" society, where globalization and technological advancements are in focus, collaborative problem-solving adeptness among our learners should be developed since it is one of the skills considered as global currency of the 21st century. This was agreed on by Fiore, Graesser, and Greiff (2018), as cited in the works of Stadler, Herborn, Mustafic, and Greiff (2020), stating that all educational systems worldwide magnified the importance of training students in acquiring collaborative problem-solving skills since employers are looking forward to workers who can work as a team towards a certain goal with less supervision for the progress of their company. Similarly, Csapó, and Funke (2017) also highlighted the importance of problem solving in this very dynamic world that envisions progress which requires students' effective problem-solving behaviors.

Life and Career Skills. These skills include adaptability, flexibility, positivity, and acceptability which lead to the development of an individual to become self-regulated and intrinsically motivated. Trilling and Fadel (2009), as cited in the study of Salas-Pilco (2013), and Eryandi and Nuryanto (2020) agreed that life and career skills that include flexibility and adaptability; self-regulatory initiative; socio-cultural interaction; productivity and accountability; and leadership and responsibility are important in a productive learning process and are highly in demand in the “k-economy”. Chalkiadaki (2018) indicated the same when he mentioned in his study that teachers must emphasize students’ development in self-motivation and their ability to lead and to take initiative since these are regarded as very important skills in the job market. This is affirmed in the study of Succi and Canovi (2020) when they revealed that it is significant for every graduate to possess the so-called soft skills, which include life and career skills, for them to acquire and develop the essential skills to adapt to the changing world and increase employment opportunities.

Abdullah, Sumarwati, and Aziz (2020) also claimed that life and career skills are “must-have” skills because most employees consider them as the “key to employment” skills that applicants should possess in order to be hired. On a similar context, in a survey conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development in 2013, the result revealed that it is vital for the 21st century workers to possess a wide range of information-processing skills and various “generic” skills which include interpersonal communication, self-management, and the ability to learn which are necessary for them to sustain the challenges that they may face in the changing world market (OECD, 2013). The same view was raised by Bridgstock (2009) as she acknowledged the importance of self-management and career building skills to lifelong career management to enhance employability.

The unemployment rate in Malaysia based on the data released by the office of the chief statistician in 2020 is increasing, and the said increase was found to be caused by the graduates’ insufficient life and career skills, making them unprepared to face the challenges of the 21st century working environment (Abdullah et al., 2020). Moreover, Azmi, Hashim, and Yusoff (2018) also claimed the same when they stated that the new graduates are half-baked since they lack the technical knowledge, creative skills, teamwork skills, oral communication skills, and decision-making skills that are highly required by employers.

Digital Literacy (Information, Media, and Technology Skills). Digital literacy, as defined in the P21st Century framework, is a combination of concepts which include information literacy; media literacy; and information and communication technology literacy (P21st Century Skills framework as cited in Khlaisang & Koraneekij, 2019). The specifics of these sub-skills based on the works of Larraz (as cited in Esteve-Mon, Llopis, & Adell-Segura, 2020), include Information Literacy (the recognition of the need of information, its location, evaluation, organization, and transformation); Technological Literacy (hardware and software management and data processing in different formats); and Multimedia Literacy (analysis, understanding, and the creation of multimedia messages).

Partnership for the 21st Century Skills Organization advocated that shaping and developing students’ digital competency should be given emphasis in all educational institutions around the globe since these are essential skills needed in meeting the

demands of the digital society (P21st Century Skills, 2018). Harper and Milman (2016) pointed out that developing students' digital competence enriches the students' learning experiences as they collaboratively work with teachers and other students. Calumba (2018), in his study on Evaluation of Teachers' Classroom Instruction, found that technology-based instruction creates a student-centered learning environment that promotes collaboration and cooperation among learners and teachers and that students are motivated to actively participate in classroom discussions and activities. He further added that using the iPad as a tool in classroom instruction provided a smooth flow in the delivery of lessons to students and offered fun and engaging learning experiences which lead to students' improved academic performance. Findikoglu and Ilhan (2016) postulated that innovation in education is the product of technology, and that technology aids in the transfer of learning to students and enhances teachers' creativity in producing instructional materials which also include production of authentic text materials to create more enhanced learning encounters. Umirova (2020) also acknowledged the importance of printed materials as a form of authentic text materials since these are full of necessary means of enhancing reading and vocabulary skills which promote learners' imagination and broaden their outlook.

Using technology as part of the teaching–learning process widens students' horizons as it provides them with the opportunity to collaborate with experts and other learners, create digital media, and utilize tools to meet their needs in attaining quality education (National Education Technology Plan, 2017). However, effective use of technology in shaping students' 21st century skills is dependent upon the teachers' successful integration of technology in the learners' learning environment (Varier, Dumke, Abrams, Conklin, Barnes, & Hoover, 2017). Dimkpa (2015) also added that powerful learning demands well-prepared teachers who draw advances in technology for them to become proficient in accessing and using information to help students appreciate learning.

The study of Esteve-Mon, Llopis, and Adell-Segura (2020) on Digital Competence and Computational Thinking of Student Teachers revealed that female student teachers have low computational and technological skills and are found to be digitally less competent than male student teachers. This only indicates that despite the efforts of all educational institutions in integrating digital competence training in their curriculum for student teachers to enable teaching such skills to their future learners successfully, a gender gap still exists in this component of the 21st century skills.

Facilitating students in their journey of acquiring the 21st century skills allowed them to be honed as career-ready and life-ready individuals who are prepared to meet the demands of the rapidly-changing economy (Di Benedetto & Myers, 2016).

Students' Profile. The students' profile that is considered in this study consist the information relevant to the students that may affect their performance in learning the 21st century skills. These include the respondents' sex and type of junior high school completed.

In the study of Goodpasture and Speece (2014), they found that women had more developed critical thinking skills than men. This finding is congruent with the PISA 2018 result which revealed that the science literacy of girls is higher than that of

the boys (Cordon & Polong, 2020). The same finding is revealed in the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), which showed that female students perform significantly better than males in Mathematics and Science (Mullis, Martin, Foy, Kelly, & Fishbein, 2020). Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics unveiled the same when they reported that female learners perform better in Reading and Writing and in Mathematics (UNICEF-SEAMEO, 2020).

Moreover, Abdullah et al. (2020) discovered in their study that in terms of life and career skills in areas such as flexibility and adaptability; social and cross-cultural skills; productivity and accountability skills; and responsibility and leadership skills, male students were found to be better than female students, but both sexes possessed the same level of initiative and self-direction skills. They stated that both male and female learners are capable of meeting goals on time and managing workloads effectively using varied strategies.

In another study conducted by Esteve-Mon et al. (2020), they disclosed that male student teachers possessed better computational and technological skills than female student teachers and that they are also more digitally competent than the females. The result agrees with the data revealed in the survey of OECD in 2013 which also claimed that men have higher scores in numeracy and problem solving in technology-rich environment than women, but the gap is not so large. Contrary to these findings, the study conducted by Lopes, Costa, Araujo, and Avila (2018) revealed that in terms of media, information, and technological skills, males and females don't show any significant difference.

On the other hand, in terms of type of schools graduated from, the PISA result unveiled that literacy skills among students in the private schools are significantly better than those who are in the public schools (OECD, 2011). In a study conducted by Ahmed, Ahmed, and Butt (2017) on the Comparative Study of Students' Academic Performance between Private and Public Higher Secondary Schools of Wah Cantt, they disclosed the same that private high school students performed better than public school students. This is affirmed in the results revealed by Natamba (2019) when he claimed that private schools have higher academic performance than public schools. Contrary to these findings, Magulod (2017) in his study on Factors of School Effectiveness and Performance of Selected Public and Private Elementary Schools claimed that public school students' academic performance is better than the private schools.

Issues and Challenges of the 21st Century Skills. The 21st century learning environment provides students the opportunities to develop their abilities to work with others and be engaged in the analysis and interpretation of data, presentation of arguments from the evidence gained, and designing scientific investigations to discover solutions (Donovan et al., 2014). The same idea is also presented by McCoog (2008), as cited in Boholano (2017), when he postulated that in order to acquire 21st century skills, students must be encouraged to create new ideas, evaluate and analyze the material presented, and apply that knowledge to their previous academic experiences.

Research findings suggest that the lower level of cognitive skills in science learning is caused by several factors. Zawilinski (2009), for instance, stressed that one

of the important components to consider in science education is the nature of its curriculum, because this dictates the competency that gives the students the opportunity to be actively engaged in higher-order thinking skills to improve their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities for them to fully understand how Science as a discipline works for the progress of the society. Another important factor to consider for effective science instruction is the learning environment where students interact with peers, classmates, and teachers and grab the chance in developing their cognitive skills. It is the appropriate venue where science education students could have the opportunity to begin thinking like scientists by engaging them in the process of thinking instead of merely ingesting the product of the scientific discoveries (Bushman & Peacock, 2010; Gillies et al., 2014).

The study of Amran, Perkasa, Satriawan, Jasin, and Irwansyah (2019) revealed that students' critical thinking ability is very low. This is because during the time of the learning process, teachers very rarely train students' critical thinking skills. Teachers only teach the concept and summative evaluation. Furthermore, they also found out that students' communication ability is categorized as low. This is because the model and method of learning that teachers use in teaching does not encourage students to develop communication and collaboration skills (as cited in Amran et al., 2019). Another study conducted by Bektas, Sellum, and Polat (2019) discovered that the students' communication and collaboration skills are good and sufficient, but they failed to develop their problem-solving, critical thinking, and creative thinking skills because teachers only provided limited learning experiences to develop these areas. The study conducted by Refugio, Galleto, and Torres (2019) found the same when they revealed that teachers also encountered challenges in teaching General Mathematics especially on problem solving because students have poor comprehension and vocabulary skills and they lack the ability to analyze; thus, they encountered difficulty in formulating the right equation.

Furthermore, according to several researchers, information literacy skills are not well taught in schools which leads to students' failure of developing such skills, hindering them to become critical and efficient users of information both printed and online informational texts (Combes, 2009; Ladbrook & Probert, 2011). They further stated that teachers were not able to successfully transmit information literacy skills because the teachers themselves also lack this knowledge. The same view is claimed by Wertz et al. (2013) when he said that information literacy was not well taught in secondary schools in New Zealand which resulted in a poor improvement in the students' information literacy skills.

Moreover, Azmi, Hashim, and Yusoff (2018) also stressed that the new graduates are half-baked since they lack the technical knowledge, creative skills, teamwork skills, oral communication skills, and decision-making skills that are highly required by employees. Meanwhile, in the study of Eryandi and Nuryanto (2020), it was revealed that students showed expertise in terms of applying life and career skills in the field of engineering, but their teachers are not as efficient as them.

The education system needs to facilitate the transition process of producing a future workforce that is equipped with the knowledge and skills to face the challenges of the 21st century (Karpudewan, 2019). One of the challenges of the 21st century is the requirement for the workers to analyze, synthesize, and evaluate any given

situation. In other words, the 21st century reinforces the fact that higher-order thinking skills must be taught to the current students' future global workforce (Osborne, 2013). The teachers must equip students with the necessary 21st century skills that would prepare them to become successful individuals in life (Wijayati, Sumarni, & Supanti, 2019). Teachers should make use of certain learning methods to help students acquire those skills (Haviz, Karomah, Delfita, Umar, & Maris, 2018).

Good teachers should know what the students need; therefore, they have to conduct research in their class (Schenzel, 2013) and optimize teacher-student dialogue (Kinchin, 2010). Teachers should be able to design a lesson that is capable of developing 21st century skills so that students are equipped with the four important aspects, namely: critical thinking skills, creative thinking skills, collaborative skills, and communicative skills (Amran et al., 2019).

Furthermore, Chu et al. (2012) stressed that educators have to continue modifying their teaching goals in order to provide students with the skills they need to contribute to their societies. As Black (2009) mentioned, with the acceleration of digital technology development in the 21st century, people are required to be equipped with skills and literacy that are important in this information age.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the extent to which teachers' practiced the 21st century skills and the Senior High School students' academic performance in their core subjects.

Specifically, it endeavors to answer the following sub-problems:

1. To what extent do the teachers practice the 21st century skills as perceived by the students in terms of the following areas:
 - 1.1 Learning and Innovation Skills;
 - 1.2 Information, Media, and Digital Literacy Skills; and
 - 1.3 Life and Career Skills?
2. What is the Grade 12 students' academic performance in the following core subjects:
 - 2.1 Oral Communication
 - 2.2 Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik;
 - 2.3 Personal Development;
 - 2.4 General Mathematics;
 - 2.5 Reading and Writing;
 - 2.6 Pagbasa;
 - 2.7 Understanding Culture;
 - 2.8 Statistics;
 - 2.9 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World;
 - 2.10 Philosophy of the Human Person;
 - 2.11 Philippine Arts;
 - 2.12 Earth and Life Science;
 - 2.13 Media and Information Literacy; and
 - 2.14 Physical Science/Disaster Risk Reduction?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills as perceived by the students and the Senior High School students' academic performance in the core subjects?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the Senior High School students' academic performance in the core subjects and their profile in terms of:
 - 4.1 sex; and
 - 4.2 Type of Junior High School completed from?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills as perceived by the students and the Senior High School students' academic performance in their core subjects.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the Senior High School students' academic performance in the core subjects and their profile.

METHODOLOGY

Research design. The descriptive–correlational design is utilized in the study. The academic performance of the Senior High School students in the 14 core subjects which measured the students' gained competence of the 21st century skills and their perceptions of their teachers' extent of practices of the 21st century skills in the classroom were described. It is correlational as well, since variables such as the extent of teachers' practices of the 21st century skills and Senior High School students' academic performance in the core subjects were correlated.

Research environment. The data-gathering process concerning students' grades was conducted in Foundation Preparatory Academy, which offers the university's basic education program. Foundation Preparatory Academy is in Dr. V. Locsin Street, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. Being one of the known private high schools in this so-called "university town", it offers quality education with emphasis on the use of technology. In its quest for excellence in mind, body, and character, the school utilizes the iPad as a tool in the teaching–learning process. Classrooms are fully air-conditioned and are equipped with flat screen televisions which are used for airplay, projecting what is shown in the iPad to the screen.

The respondents of the study are the Senior High School graduates of Foundation Preparatory Academy, Dumaguete City Division, for the academic years 2017–2018, 2018–2019, and 2019–2020. They are the first three batches of Senior High School students under the K-12 curriculum who graduated from the Foundation Preparatory Academy. Out of 1,318 graduates, 348 of them answered the questionnaires in Google forms sent via messenger. This number is enough to represent the population using the sampling formula. These students took up the Academic Track, Technical and Vocational Track, and Arts and Design Track.

Research instruments. The researcher used the grades of the three batches of Senior High School students who graduated from Foundation Preparatory Academy during the academic years 2017–2018; 2018–2019; and 2019–2020.

An adopted open-source questionnaire from Bukidnon State University was also utilized in the study to determine the teachers' extent of practice of the 21st century

skills in their classroom as perceived by their students. The questionnaire is composed of two parts. The first part is the student respondents' profile which includes their sex and type of junior high school where one completed from. The second part is focused on the practices of teachers of the 21st century skills in delivering instruction in the classroom and is composed of three areas, namely: learning and innovation skills; information, media, and technology skills; and life and career skills.

The entire questionnaire was presented to three experts for content validity and cross checking if the items are aligned with the specific problems of the study.

To ensure item reliability, a dry-run was also conducted. There were 30 students who served as the respondents. Using Cronbach's Alpha Test, results revealed the following reliability coefficients: 0.809 for Learning and Innovation Skills; 0.765 for Information and Media and Digital Literacy Skills; and 0.813 for Life and Career Skills. These figures were greater than 0.70 which implied that items were reliable.

Research procedure. The researcher at first sought for approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of Foundation University for the administration of her questionnaire to the respondents of her study who graduated from Foundation Preparatory Academy and are now in their college years at the different colleges and universities in the Philippines. After which, the researcher asked from the Foundation Preparatory Academy Guidance Office, with the approval of the principal, for the complete list of the three batches of Senior High School graduates for her reference in reaching out to them for the floating of her questionnaires.

Furthermore, the researcher wrote a letter through email to the authors asking permission on the use of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was encoded in Google forms so that it could be accessed by the respondents easily via messenger and Facebook.

A letter of formal request asking for the grades of the Senior High School graduates was sent to the Principal of Foundation Preparatory Academy upon the endorsement of the Dean of the Graduate School of Foundation University. The signed and approved request, together with another letter of request addressed to the Dean of Admission and Records, was given to the registrar's office asking permission to access the grades of the Senior High School graduates of academic years 2017–2018; 2018–2019; and 2019–2020 who responded the researchers' questionnaire sent in Google forms via messenger.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools that the researcher utilized in this study are the following:

Chi-square. This was used to identify the relationship between the students' profile (sex and junior high school completed from) and their academic performance in their Senior High School core subjects. This test is applicable since the profile is in nominal scale.

Mean. This was used in getting the average rating of students' academic performance in their Senior High School core subjects. This was also used in determining the teachers' extent of practice of the 21st century skills in their classrooms as perceived by the students.

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the teachers' extent of practice of the 21st century skills as perceived by the students and the students' academic performance in their Senior High School core subjects. This test was selected again since the data are in ordinal scale.

The academic performance of the Senior High School students in the core subjects is based on the following criteria (DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015).

Rating	Verbal Equivalent	Explanation
90% and above	Outstanding	The learner at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understanding, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
85-89%	Very Satisfactory	The learner at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understanding, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
80-84%	Satisfactory	The learner at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understanding, and with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75-79%	Fairly Satisfactory	The learner at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectation	The learner at this level struggles with his/her understanding; pre-requisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

The Teachers' Extent of Practice of the 21st century skills is quantified according to the following scale:

Score	Verbal Description	Extent of Practice	Scale	Explanation
7	Always	Very High	6.15 – 7.00	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 87–100% of the time.
6	Usually	High	5.29 – 6.14	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 73–86% of the time.
5	Frequently	Somewhat High	4.43 – 5.28	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 59–72% of the time.
4	Sometimes	Moderate	3.57 – 4.42	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 43–58% of the time.
3	Occasionally	Somewhat Low	2.71 – 3.56	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 29–42% of the time.
2	Rarely	Low	1.85 – 2.70	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 15–28% of the time.
1	Never	Very Low	1.00 – 1.84	The domains of the 21 st century skills are practiced by the teachers 1–14% of the time.

Scope of the study. This study primarily focused on the extent of teachers' practices of the 21st century skills in the delivery of their classroom instructions and the Senior High School students' academic performance in their core subjects. Students' profile, which include sex and type of junior high school completed from, are also included as variables in this study since these are also believed to influence students' academic performance.

Limitations of the study. The study utilized the three batches of grade 12 students who graduated from Foundation Preparatory Academy for the academic years 2017–2018; 2018–2019; and 2019–2020. Since these students are now studying at different colleges and universities in Negros Oriental, Cebu, and as far as Manila and Mindanao, the students' responses in answering the questionnaires as to

the extent to which their Senior High School teachers practiced the 21st century skills were limited; the researcher only counted on the students who could still be reached through social media (messenger and Facebook).

Since this study used a questionnaire in Google form, as an instrument in gathering the data on students' perceptions, the researcher relied on the honesty of the students in answering every item or indicator in the questionnaire, especially that they answered the questionnaire electronically. Hence, there can be a trace of bias.

RESULTS

Table 1.1

Teachers' Extent of Practice as Perceived by the Students in the area of Learning and Innovation Skills of the 21st Century Skills (n = 348)

My teachers...	w \bar{x}	VD	EIP
1. Create collaborative group activities to encourage participation and shared leadership.	6.20	A	VH
2. Provide learners with performance standards by which their work will be evaluated.	6.08	U	H
3. Bring together relevant information and perspectives to inform thoughts, actions, or beliefs of learners.	6.05	U	H
4. Synthesize and interpret information by asking essential questions that help clarify a path towards better solutions.	6.04	U	H
5. Respect the views of learners and others when expressing opinions or ideas without bias.	6.02	U	H
6. Allow an open conference style of interaction rather than the one-way seating of traditional desk.	5.95	U	H
7. Focus on project-based learning which enables learners to put knowledge together in the form of focused questions and assessments for the project.	5.93	U	H
8. Brainstorm and seek out opportunities for learners to improve their ideas and on the way they react to situations.	5.91	U	H
9. Support or empower learners who are reluctant to share their knowledge or views.	5.90	U	H
10. Use engaging instructional strategies suitable to instructional purposes and learners' levels and learning styles.	5.89	U	H
11. Select problems that are applicable to real-life situations and let the learners find solutions for it.	5.89	U	H
12. Ensure that a more comprehensive approach to inquiry that includes reflection is used in the classroom.	5.88	U	H
13. Consider contexts or incorporate different perspectives to evaluate thoughts or actions.	5.88	U	H
14. Guide the learners in examining reliability, bias, or credibility of claims by means of giving activities that suit to it.	5.86	U	H
15. Facilitate the learners in organizing, classifying, questioning, or evaluating the work of their classmates.	5.82	U	H
16. Observe the learners while they are having the self-learning in the classroom.	5.81	U	H
17. Break problems into smaller or simpler parts and develop criteria in solving problems.	5.81	U	H

18. Make graphic organizers to illustrate difficult topics.	5.79	U	H
19. Manipulate models and simulations for the learners to experiment and create new ideas.	5.78	U	H
20. Prepare some worksheets for the learners to answer after watching relevant videos.	5.74	U	H
Composite	5.91	U	H

Legend: Range	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Instructional Practice (EIP)
6.15 – 7.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	Usually (U)	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Frequently (F)	Somewhat High (SH)
3.57 – 4.42	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
2.71 – 3.56	Occasionally (O)	Somewhat Low (SL)
1.85 – 2.70	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.2

Teachers' Extent of Practice as Perceived by the Students in the area of Information, Media, and Digital Literacy of the 21st Century Skills (n = 348)

My teachers...	w \bar{x}	VD	EIP
1. Communicate to students by means of social media.	6.24	A	VH
2. Access internet resources for planning instruction or collecting ideas.	6.23	A	VH
3. Educate learners on how to use computers for learning.	6.15	A	VH
4. Find resources such as databases, documentary films, and websites to be utilized in class as sources of information.	6.12	U	H
5. Provide opportunities for learners to gather information online.	6.12	U	H
6. Make internet as a tool for giving learners assessments and assignments.	6.11	U	H
7. Use PowerPoint presentation with moving clip art or animation for them to feel and catch the attention of the students.	6.08	U	H
8. Help the learners recognize the false information in all forms of media.	6.05	U	H
9. Participate in accessing information in an effective manner which is related to the learners' learning.	6.04	U	H
10. Incorporate and integrate different forms of media into instruction.	6.04	U	H
11. Encourage collaborative learning in order to participate effectively and generate valuable information.	6.01	U	H
12. Offer a variety of ways for learners to repackage information and authentic media learning experience.	6.01	U	H
13. Update students on educational trends and issues through internet access.	5.98	U	H
14. Help the learners appreciate literature and other creative expressions of information.	5.97	U	H
15. Utilize the e-class record in determining learners' achievements.	5.95	U	H
16. Use ICT in creating materials for learners' use.	5.94	U	H

17. Evaluate the resources and the available information.	5.93	U	H
18. Submit computer-generated reports.	5.91	U	H
19. Use interactive technology for learning such as school-purchased instructional software.	5.91	U	H
20. Make printed materials in remediation for slow learners.	5.31	U	H
Composite	6.01	U	H

Legend: Range	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Instructional Practice (EIP)
6.15 – 7.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	Usually (U)	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Frequently (F)	Somewhat High (SH)
3.57 – 4.42	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
2.71 – 3.56	Occasionally (O)	Somewhat Low (SL)
1.85 – 2.70	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.3

Teachers' Extent of Practice as Perceived by the Students in the area of Life and Career Skills of the 21st Century Skills (n = 348)

My teachers.....	w \bar{x}	VD	EIP
1. Respect cultural differences and work effectively with people from a range of social and cultural backgrounds.	6.28	A	VH
2. Give value and respect to other people's opinions, ideas, and beliefs.	6.26	A	VH
3. Has the innate ability to inspire, energize, and encourage the learners and everyone.	6.21	A	VH
4. Build harmonious relationships with the learners by knowing when to talk and when to listen.	6.17	A	VH
5. Collaborate and cooperate effectively with team.	6.15	A	VH
6. Treat each learner as an individual deserving of respect and not as a representative of a group.	6.14	U	H
7. Establish commitment to learning as a lifelong process.	6.14	U	H
8. Ensure that learners' differences are accepted and the needs of individual learners are addressed to the best extent possible, regardless of their background.	6.13	U	H
9. Practice cooperative learning by encouraging cooperative learning tasks and discouraging negative competition among learners.	6.13	U	H
10. Delegate some tasks that learners can easily do on their own.	6.10	U	H
11. Able to adapt to any changes that may occur in the learning environment.	6.07	U	H
12. Participate in trainings that promote peace and understanding of cultural diversity.	6.06	U	H
13. Reflect critically on past experiences in order to inform future progress.	6.06	U	H
14. Keep things balanced, not only tasks and responsibilities, but also the diverse views and belief to reach workable solutions, particularly in a multicultural environment.	6.03	U	H
15. Negotiate to teach a peaceable resolution or compromise acceptance to everyone.	6.03	U	H

16. Design learning activities that reflect the different backgrounds and needs of the students.	6.01	U	H
17. Go beyond basic mastery of the skills and curriculum to explore and expand one's own learning and opportunities to gain expertise.	6.00	U	H
18. Utilize time and manage workload efficiently.	5.97	U	H
19. Select materials that reflect the different backgrounds and needs of the learners.	5.96	U	H
20. Manage and document conflicts that arise in the classroom.	5.90	U	H
Composite	6.09	U	H

Legend: Range	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Instructional Practice (EIP)
6.15 – 7.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	Usually (U)	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Frequently (F)	Somewhat High (SH)
3.57 – 4.42	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
2.71 – 3.56	Occasionally (O)	Somewhat Low (SL)
1.85 – 2.70	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2

Senior High School Students' Academic Performance in Core Subjects (n = 348)

Core Subjects	Mean	Sd	Verbal Description
1. Media and Information Literacy	92.25	3.96	Outstanding
2. Personal Development	92.21	5.33	Outstanding
3. Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions	91.80	4.61	Outstanding
4. Earth and Life Science/Earth Science	91.41	4.54	Outstanding
5. Physical Science/Disaster Risk Reduction and Management	91.22	4.66	Outstanding
6. Pagbasa at Pagsulat ng ibat-ibang texto tungo sa Pananaliksik	90.92	4.99	Outstanding
7. Oral Communication	90.38	4.54	Outstanding
8. Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika at Kulturang Filipino	90.35	3.60	Outstanding
9. Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics	89.78	4.94	Outstanding
10. General Mathematics	89.64	4.68	Outstanding
11. Statistics and Probability	89.62	5.15	Outstanding
12. Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person	89.26	4.46	Very Satisfactory
13. 21 st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World	88.89	6.07	Very Satisfactory
14. Reading and Writing	87.65	5.48	Very Satisfactory
Average	90.38	4.79	Outstanding

Legend: Rating	Verbal Description
90% - 100%	Outstanding
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
80% - 84%	Satisfactory
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
74% and Below	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 3

Relationship between Teachers' Extent of Practice of the 21st Century Skills as Perceived by the Students and Students' Academic Performance in the Core Subjects (n = 348)

Core Subjects	Learning & Innovation Skills	Info., Media & Literacy Skills	Life and Career Skills	Overall
1. Oral Communication	$r_s = 0.012$ $p = 0.818$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.055$ $p = 0.309$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.041$ $p = 0.443$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.036$ $p = 0.509$ (not significant)
2. Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika at Kulturang Filipino	$r_s = -0.042$ $p = 0.435$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.003$ $p = 0.955$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.023$ $p = 0.672$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.030$ $p = 0.577$ (not significant)
3. Personal Development	$r_s = -0.091$ $p = 0.089$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.045$ $p = 0.403$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.076$ $p = 0.158$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.086$ $p = 0.111$ (not significant)
4. General Mathematics	$r_s = -0.116$ $p = 0.030$ (significant)	$r_s = -0.084$ $p = 0.118$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.061$ $p = 0.256$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.099$ $p = 0.065$ (not significant)
5. Reading and Writing	$r_s = 0.027$ $p = 0.619$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.004$ $p = 0.941$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.002$ $p = 0.976$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.017$ $p = 0.751$ (not significant)
6. Pagbasa at Pagsulat ng ibat-ibang texto tungo sa Pananaliksik	$r_s = -0.022$ $p = 0.681$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.002$ $p = 0.972$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.005$ $p = 0.932$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.013$ $p = 0.808$ (not significant)
7. Understanding Culture, Society and Politics	$r_s = -0.056$ $p = 0.297$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.055$ $p = 0.305$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.035$ $p = 0.512$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.061$ $p = 0.259$ (not significant)
8. Statistics and Probability	$r_s = 0.015$ $p = 0.782$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.023$ $p = 0.667$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.018$ $p = 0.739$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.016$ $p = 0.772$ (not significant)
9. 21 st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World	$r_s = -0.025$ $p = 0.635$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.003$ $p = 0.951$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.025$ $p = 0.648$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.010$ $p = 0.852$ (not significant)
10. Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person	$r_s = -0.108$ $p = 0.045$ (significant)	$r_s = -0.086$ $p = 0.109$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.096$ $p = 0.072$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.115$ $p = 0.033$ (significant)
11. Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions	$r_s = 0.073$ $p = 0.175$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.088$ $p = 0.100$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.075$ $p = 0.162$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.080$ $p = 0.138$ (not significant)
12. Earth and Life Science /Earth Science	$r_s = -0.064$ $p = 0.232$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.031$ $p = 0.568$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.025$ $p = 0.637$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.050$ $p = 0.349$ (not significant)
13. Media and Information Literacy	$r_s = -0.061$ $p = 0.255$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.070$ $p = 0.192$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.048$ $p = 0.369$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.058$ $p = 0.285$ (not significant)
14. Physical Science/Disaster Risk Reduction and Management	$r_s = -0.035$ $p = 0.520$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.012$ $p = 0.822$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.031$ $p = 0.561$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.031$ $p = 0.563$ (not significant)
Average	$r_s = -0.042$ $p = 0.432$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.007$ $p = 0.896$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.012$ $p = 0.818$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.031$ $p = 0.563$ (not significant)

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 4

Relationship between Students' Profile and their Academic Performance in the Core Subjects (n = 348)

Core Subjects	Sex	Mean	Type of JHS	Mean
1. Oral Communication	$\chi^2 = 8.447$ $p = 0.005$ (significant)	Male: 89.53 Female: 90.94	$\chi^2 = 9.610$ $p = 0.008$ (significant)	Private: 89.53 Public: 91.23
2. Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika at Kult. Fil.	$\chi^2 = 23.158$ $p = 0.000$ (significant)	Male: 89.36 Female: 91.00	$\chi^2 = 3.941$ $p = 0.139$ (not significant)	Private: 89.94 Public: 90.76
3. Personal Development	$\chi^2 = 3.357$ $p = 0.187$ (not significant)	Male: 91.65 Female: 92.58	$\chi^2 = 9.537$ $p = 0.008$ (significant)	Private: 91.15 Public: 93.26
4. General Mathematics	$\chi^2 = 3.009$ $p = 0.222$ (not significant)	Male: 89.21 Female: 89.94	$\chi^2 = 1.660$ $p = 0.436$ (not significant)	Private: 89.24 Public: 90.04
5. Reading and Writing	$\chi^2 = 4.336$ $p = 0.114$ (not significant)	Male: 87.06 Female: 88.04	$\chi^2 = 0.959$ $p = 0.619$ (not significant)	Private: 87.43 Public: 87.86
6. Pagbasa at Pagsulat ng ibat-ibang Texto tungo sa Pananaliksik	$\chi^2 = 9.962$ $p = 0.007$ (significant)	Male: 89.79 Female: 91.67	$\chi^2 = 4.257$ $p = 0.119$ (not significant)	Private: 90.08 Public: 91.76
7. Understanding Culture, Society and Politics	$\chi^2 = 6.119$ $p = 0.047$ (significant)	Male: 88.81 Female: 90.42	$\chi^2 = 1.707$ $p = 0.436$ (not significant)	Private: 89.46 Public: 90.09
8. Statistics and Probability	$\chi^2 = 8.247$ $p = 0.016$ (significant)	Male: 88.53 Female: 90.34	$\chi^2 = 5.250$ $p = 0.072$ (not significant)	Private: 88.84 Public: 90.39
9. 21 st Century Lit. from the Philippines and the World	$\chi^2 = 8.039$ $p = 0.018$ (significant)	Male: 87.65 Female: 89.74	$\chi^2 = 2.252$ $p = 0.324$ (not significant)	Private: 88.83 Public: 88.98
10. Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person	$\chi^2 = 17.733$ $p = 0.000$ (significant)	Male: 88.06 Female: 90.05	$\chi^2 = 0.589$ $p = 0.754$ (not significant)	Private: 89.23 Public: 89.28
11. Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions	$\chi^2 = 3.520$ $p = 0.172$ (not significant)	Male: 91.31 Female: 92.12	$\chi^2 = 3.323$ $p = 0.190$ (not significant)	Private: 91.13 Public: 92.47
12. Earth and Life Science/Earth Science	$\chi^2 = 13.655$ $p = 0.001$ (significant)	Male: 90.34 Female: 92.11	$\chi^2 = 7.210$ $p = 0.027$ (significant)	Private: 90.65 Public: 92.16
13. Media and Information Literacy	$\chi^2 = 6.164$ $p = 0.046$ (significant)	Male: 91.54 Female: 92.73	$\chi^2 = 0.271$ $p = 0.873$ (not significant)	Private: 91.95 Public: 92.55
14. Physical Science/ Disaster Risk Reduction & Mgt	$\chi^2 = 9.322$ $p = 0.009$ (significant)	Male: 90.42 Female: 91.76	$\chi^2 = 2.817$ $p = 0.244$ (not significant)	Private: 90.77 Public: 91.68
Average	$\chi^2 = 13.560$ $p = 0.001$ (significant)	Male: 89.52 Female: 90.96	$\chi^2 = 7.122$ $p = 0.028$ (significant)	Private: 89.87 Public: 90.89

Level of significance = 0.05

DISCUSSION

Shown in Table 1.1 on the next page is the extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills as perceived by their students in the area of Learning and Innovation Skills. It can be noticed that indicator no.1 on creating collaborative group activities to encourage participation and shared leadership got the highest weighted mean of 6.20 which is Very High. Moreover, the data display that Senior High School students observed that their teachers have Highly practiced the rest of the indicators with mean ratings ranging from 5.74 to 6.08, such as: (a) providing learners with performance standards; (b) bringing together relevant information; (c) synthesizing and interpreting information by asking essential questions; (d) respecting the views of learners; (e) allowing an open conference style; (f) focusing on project-based learning; and other indicators as reflected in the data. The result suggests that the FPA educators teaching the young generation of today made a shift from the traditional way of teaching, in which students will just sit at a corner and passively listen, to the “constructivists” approach wherein learners actively participate through collaboration with others, not just for their own learning but also for the development of their collaboration skills.

It can be deduced from these results that the teachers act as facilitators of learning, while the opportunities to learn and explore are given to the students. The findings are in agreement to Magno et al. (2016), when they suggested that teachers should set a learning environment where authentic learning opportunities are provided to develop the learners’ potentials and capabilities to their fullest extent and to produce proficient individuals bestowed with the 21st century skills. Atalay and Boyaci (2019) also pointed out that students could successfully develop learning and innovation skills when they are properly facilitated by their teachers and appropriate instructional materials and learning environment are provided.

The result reveals that the teachers’ overall extent of practice on learning and innovation skills is High, with a composite weighted mean of 5.91. This entails that the students are able to observe that their teachers practiced the domains of the 21st century skills, which include Collaboration, Creativity and Innovation, Communication, and Critical Thinking and Problem Solving (4Cs), 73%–86% of the time in their delivery of teaching.

This finding is in line with the works of Stadler et al. (2020), where they highlighted that all learning institutions should magnify the importance of training students’ collaborative problem-solving skills as employers put high regard to workers who can work as a team to produce high-quality outcomes. Newland (2016) claimed the same when he stressed that there is an urgent need for students to develop collaborative problem-solving adeptness for this is one of the skills that is considered as global currency of the 21st century. These assertions are further strengthened by Anagun et al. (2015) who posited that it is vital for teachers and the school to prepare students for social and economic life by equipping them with all the sub-skills of Learning and Innovation skills for them to successfully thrive.

Presented in Table 1.2 are the data on teachers' extent of practice of the 21st century skills in the area of Information, Media, and Digital Literacy Skills. The result reflects that the Senior High School students agreed that their teachers Highly practiced the area on Information, Media, and Literacy Skills, as shown in its composite weighted mean of 6.01. It can be gleaned from the data, specifically indicators 1, 2, and 3, that the students witnessed that their teachers' extent of practices in terms of (a) communicating to students by means of social media; (b) accessing internet resources for planning instruction or collecting ideas; and (c) educating learners on how to use computers for learning is Very High. It is observable from the result that teachers teach their students flexibility and self-directed learning to reinforce students' abilities to explore and search valid information. This indicates that teachers put emphasis in the use of digital tools as means of supporting active interaction with their students for a dynamic and productive learning environment.

In the 2017 update of the National Education Technology Plan, it was highlighted that using technology in instructional learning increases students' opportunity to attain quality learning through collaboration and utilization of digital media and tools. In line with this, Varier et al. (2017) prompted teachers that the effective integration of technology in classroom instruction must be observed to successfully shape the learners' 21st century skills. Dimkpa (2015) also added that powerful learning demands well-prepared teachers who draw advances in technology for them to become proficient in accessing and using information to help students appreciate learning. The use of technology creates a learning environment where the learners are placed at the center of the educative process and are made to realize that they are responsible for their own learning.

Furthermore, it can also be seen from the presented data that Senior High School students rated High in most of the indicators, as evidenced by the values of their weighted mean ranging from 5.31 to 6.12 which include: (a) finding resources such as databases, documentary films, and websites to be utilized in class; (b) providing opportunities to learners to gather information; (c) making internet as a tool for assessments; (d) using PowerPoint presentation with animation; (e) helping learners recognize false information in all forms of media; (f) participating in assessing information in an effective manner which is related to the learners' learning; (g) incorporating and integrating different forms of media in classroom teaching; (h) encouraging collaborative learning in order to participate actively and generate valuable information; (i) offering a variety of ways for learners to repackage information and authentic media learning experience; and others.

Moreover, it can be noted that making printed materials in remediation for slow learners is rated the lowest, as shown in its weighted mean of 5.31. The result can be ascribed to the current nature of the 21st century classroom where misconceptions arise because some teachers, including learners, believed that since they are already well grounded in digital technology, printed materials are not any more effective and suited to them. This idea contrasts the findings of Omirova (2020) as she disclosed that printed materials are important to enrich students' reading and comprehension skills because they bear interesting and real features for learners to learn new things autonomously, thus leading to a more meaningful learning.

Shown in Table 1.3 is the result on the extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills on the area of Life and Career Skills. As indicated in the results, Foundation Preparatory Academy teachers Highly practiced Life and Career Skills in their 21st century instruction. Life and Career Skills support every individual's journey to successfully deal with the challenges of life, thus providing a strong foundation to overcome and thrive in this very dynamic society. The findings infer that the teachers cultivate in learners the ability to traverse the complex life and explore the very competitive world brought about by the industrial revolution 4.0. Dimkpa (2015) believed that when teachers practice Life and Career Skills to a high extent, it follows that students also demonstrate strong life and career skills which they can apply in the workplace. Abdullah et al. (2020) specified that employers considered life and career skills as the "key to employment skills"; thus, it is imperative that learners should possess such competency.

The findings of Bridgstock (2009) confirmed that self-management and career building skills are important to lifelong career management to augment employability rate among young individuals. Succi and Cannovi (2020) presented a similar observation when she found in her study that learners must take the responsibility to acquire and develop the essential soft skills which include self-motivation, establishing an atmosphere of cooperation and collaboration where different views are heard and respected, and the willingness to help others for learners to easily adapt to changes. The same emphasis is found in the result of the study as it can be gleaned from the data that indicators 1 to 5, which talk about (a) respecting cultural differences and working effectively with people from a range of social and cultural backgrounds; (b) giving value and respecting other people's opinions, ideas, and beliefs; (c) having the innate ability to inspire, energize, and encourage learners; (d) building harmonious relationship with the learners; and (e) collaborating and cooperating effectively with the team, are practiced by the teachers at a Very High extent, as shown by the weighted mean which ranges from 6.15 to 6.28.

Table 2 presents the Senior High School students' academic performance in the core subjects. As shown in the results, Senior High School students exhibit "Outstanding" performance in Media and Information Literacy, Personal Development, Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions, Earth and Life Science, Physical Science, Pagbasa at Pagsulat, Oral Communication, Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika, Understanding Culture and Society, General Mathematics and Statistics with mean ratings ranging from 89.62 to 92.25. This indicates that the Senior High School students' performances of Foundation Preparatory Academy exceeded the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understanding the core subjects, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks (DepEd Order No.8, s. 2015). The result is a gauge that the students are shaped and prepared to thrive in a globally competitive society.

Meanwhile, Senior High School students' academic performance in Introduction to Philosophy, 21st Century Literature, and Reading and Writing is on the "Very Satisfactory" level with mean ratings of 89.26; 88.89; and 87.65, respectively. Since all 21st century competencies such as critical thinking, complex problem solving, collaboration, communication and multimedia skills are intertwined into all content areas in the core subjects, the result denotes that students have mastered the 21st century competencies and are globally competitive as evidenced by their outstanding

and very satisfactory performances. The result corresponds to the findings of Rahman (2019) when he emphasized in his study that students have to gain more knowledge in all subject areas to lead a successful life and, at the same time, gain important skills which will help them survive in the fast-changing world.

This matches to the findings of Rotherham and Willingham (as cited in the works of Magno et al., 2016) which revealed that business leaders, politicians, and educators agreed that students must be equipped with the necessary 21st century skills so that they are prepared to compete in the global market. Furthermore, Ross (2017) claimed that providing students with the 21st century skills does not only provide them with the framework for successful learning but it also armed them with the required skills to successfully thrive in this k-economy society. In addition, Rahman (2019) stressed that students must be knowledgeable on different subject areas to become productive beings.

Moreover, it can further be noted from the data that the Senior High School students' performance in Media and Information Literacy has the highest mean rating of 92.25 with a verbal description of "Outstanding". The result could be attributed to Foundation Preparatory Academy's emphasis in the use of technology, particularly the iPad as a tool in developing the mind, body, and character of every learner. It is evident from the findings that FPA teachers successfully integrated digital tools in the teaching-learning process which contributed to the students' outstanding academic performance in Media and Information Literacy. This was supported in the study of Calumba (2018), when he found that Foundation Preparatory Academy teachers' use of technology, particularly the iPad in classroom instruction, creates a student-centered learning environment that addresses students' different learning styles and caters to the needs of every learner, thus improving their academic performance. He further claimed that using technology-based instruction promotes collaboration and cooperation among students as they enthusiastically engage in every learning activity provided by the teachers.

Furthermore, Calisang et al. (2019) in her study on Students' Attitude towards E-learning in relation to their Learning Styles also mentioned that FPA students exhibit positive attitude towards the use of iPad as a tool in classroom learning and in E-learning, in general, because it provided them a wide variety of interesting and exciting learning experiences as they can freely explore with their teachers and classmates for productive learning purposes. She also found that E-learning accommodates learners of different learning styles, and trained them to become independent and inquisitive since it provided the learners with a self-paced learning environment. These findings only proved that Foundation Preparatory Academy is successful in responding to the advocacy of Partnership for the 21st Century Skills Organization of all educational institutions to give emphasis in shaping and developing students' digital competence which includes media and information literacy skills to address the needs of the digital society (P21st Century Skills, 2018).

It can be seen from the data that the teachers' effective use of technology in the teaching-learning process creates a meaningful and interesting learning environment which leads to the learners' productive learning experience. The result is parallel to the study of Findikoglu and Ilhan (2016) as they pointed out that technology paved the way for teachers to create attractive and interactive instructional materials,

which supports the transfer of learning to students and develops their digital competence, thus leading to an improved academic performance. This marks the shift in the educational system from the traditional rote memorization of facts to technology integration that helps in the development of the 21st century skills in learners such as creativity; critical thinking; communication; collaboration; problem solving; and media and technological skills (Urbani et al., 2017; Van Laar et al., 2017).

On the other hand, of the 14 core subjects, it can be observed that the students' academic performance in Reading and Writing is the lowest with a mean rating of 87.65 and a verbal description of "Very Satisfactory". The finding is similar to the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment of the Organization for Economic Cooperation results which revealed that Filipino students ranked second to the last in Reading Literacy, out of the 79 participating countries with an average score of 340 points which is lower than the OECD average of 487 points (PISA, 2018). This means that English teachers must go the extra mile by giving more activities for practice and assessment, such as essay writing, composing varied forms of professional correspondence and assignments on readings from scholarly journals and book reviews, to develop students' love for reading and writing and to sharpen their skills in composition. This is affirmed in the works of Umirova (2020) as the author pointed out that authentic text materials, such as printed materials which improve learners' reading comprehension, vocabulary, writing, and grammatical skills, will also further develop their fundamental critical and analytical thinking skills.

Table 3 depicts the results on the relationship between the extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills as perceived by the students and the students' academic performance in the core subjects. The data indicate that there is an inverse and significant relationship ($p < \alpha = 0.05$) between the extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills in terms of learning and innovation skills and students' performance in General Mathematics ($r_s = - 0.116$; $p = 0.030$) and Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person ($r_s = - 0.108$; $p = 0.045$). This finding may imply that students with lower academic performance in General Mathematics and Philosophy of the Human Person have teachers who displayed higher extent of practice on the 21st century skills in terms of Learning and Innovation skills.

Mathematics and Philosophy subjects are challenging areas in the field of formal and social sciences because these cover topics and competencies that require a lot of analysis or deep and sound critical thinking — the strong foundation in reasoning and problem-solving processes.

In line with this, it can be observed from the results that Mathematics and Philosophy teachers Highly practiced Learning and Innovation skills which include the 4Cs (Communication, Critical thinking and problem solving, Creativity, and Collaboration) and devote extra time in teaching the concepts in order to improve the students' grades, but the students have not yet reached the outstanding level of their performance. This is in consonance with the findings of Refugio et al. (2019), as they revealed that Mathematics teachers tend to put extra time and extend more sessions when they reach the problem-solving concepts in Mathematics because students encountered difficulty in understanding and analyzing worded problems. The researchers interviewed their teacher respondents and found that the problem is due to students' poor comprehension and analytical skills.

This is also similar to the claims of FPA Mathematics and Philosophy teachers when they expressed during the interview that the leading challenge they come across in teaching the previously mentioned subjects is students' poor comprehension and analytical skills, so students cannot effectively connect equations and representations in the area of Mathematics and situational axioms in Philosophy to arrive at the correct solutions to worded problems and valid reasons to the maxims. This is confirmed in the statement of Tchoshanov as cited in the works of Refugio et al. (2019), when they pointed out that the difficulty of the subject on the area of problem solving is ascribed to students' weak connection between situations, concepts, comprehension, and representations.

In the teaching of General Mathematics and Introduction to Philosophy subjects, English is used as the medium of instruction. However, despite the fact that English is the second language, it cannot be denied that the students have difficulty in reading comprehension; thus, this becomes a barrier in the teaching–learning process. The teachers even spent more time to explain the worded problems and theorems, including the presented arguments, before the students can establish the connections. These claims can be attributed to students' poor reading and comprehension skills. This can be the underlying reasons on why an inverse relationship between the teachers' practices on the 21st century skills on Learning and Innovation (with the emphasis on 4Cs) and the students' academic performance in Mathematics and Philosophy exists because it can be gleaned from the results in Table 2 that in all of their core subject grades, reading got the lowest rating.

The data also reflect that there is an inverse and significant relationship ($p < \alpha = 0.05$) between the overall extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills and the students' performance in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person ($r_s = -0.115$; $p = 0.033$). This finding may imply that students with lower academic performance in Philosophy of the Human Person have teachers who have displayed higher 21st century skills. Philosophy as a subject does not require memorization but rather the ability to evaluate arguments that requires excellent critical thinking and strong reasoning skills to back up opinions on given issues. In this regard, Zulkifli and Hashim (2020) suggested that teachers must be proficient in providing a learning environment and situations with learning stimuli that spark students' interest to actively engage in order to develop their critical thinking skills. In a study that they conducted on the application of philosophy with the emphasis on the development of 4Cs, they found that students' 4Cs are less developed because they lack the strong foundation in reading and critical thinking due to the lack of opportunities for intellectual stimulation that could reinforce and enhance their prior literacy experience.

Meanwhile, the rest of the paired variables do not indicate significant relationships ($p > 0.05$). This may mean that (a) Learning and Innovation Skills, (b) Information, Media, and Literacy Skills, and (c) Life and Career Skills cannot be considered as determinant of students' performance in most of their core subjects. This may be due to the responses of the students that do not vary much as reflected in the raw data and as shown in Tables 1.1–1.3.

Table 4 reflects the mean performances of the students when grouped according to their sex. As shown, the mean performances of the female students are higher than the male students and statistically significant ($p < \alpha = 0.05$) in the following

core subjects: Oral Communication ($p = 0.005$); Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika at Kulturang Filipino ($p = 0.000$); Pagbasa at Pagsulat ng ibat-ibang Texto Tungo sa Pananaliksik ($p = 0.007$); Understanding Culture, Society and Politics ($p = 0.047$); Statistics and Probability ($p = 0.016$); 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World ($p = 0.018$); Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person ($p = 0.000$); Earth and Life Science/Earth Science ($p = 0.001$); Media and Information Literacy (0.046); and Physical Science/Disaster Risk Reduction and Management ($p = 0.009$). This means that female students perform better than the male students on the mentioned subjects. The result of the study is similar to the findings of the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics which disclosed that female learners perform better in reading and writing and in mathematics literacy than males (UNICEF-SEAMEO, 2020). The same finding is discovered in the results of the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study, which revealed that female students performed significantly better than male students in Mathematics and Science (Mullis et al., 2020). The result suggests that female students can competently master the content and skills and, at the same time, can manage their time wisely, so they can produce quality outputs better than males in the enumerated core subjects.

The result contradicts the findings of Esteve-Mon et al. (2020) when they pointed out that females have low computational and technological skills and are digitally less competent than males. In another study conducted by Lopes et al. (2018), the result disclosed that Media and Information Literacy skills of male and female students do not vary. This is further supported in the OECD (2013) survey result which denotes that differences in literacy skills between males and females do not exist.

In terms of the type of junior high school completed from, students coming from public high schools have higher mean performances than those students coming from private schools and statistically significant ($p < \alpha = 0.05$) only in the following core subjects: Oral Communication ($p = 0.008$); Personal Development ($p = 0.008$); and Earth and Life Science/Earth Science ($p = 0.027$). This signifies that students from public junior high schools perform better than those students from private junior high schools on the enumerated core subjects. The result negates the common notion that students from the private schools perform better than those in the public schools. This is supported by the findings of Magulod (2017) when he discovered in his study that in terms of the level of school performances as revealed in the National Achievement Tests for the three (3) consecutive years, public schools showed better academic performance than the private schools. The results can be attributed to the government's efforts to make educational reforms in the Philippine educational system, such as setting aside the biggest chunk of the national budget to the education sector to increase the provision of more classrooms, to improve the school facilities and the schools' computerization programs and ICT packages, and to uplift the standards of teachers through the provision of professional development training and salary increase for teachers to offer a better school climate and quality education. The finding is in opposition to the results of the study conducted by Ahmed et al. (2017), Natamba (2019), and the OECD PISA 2018 result which unveiled that private school students perform better than those in the public schools.

Conclusions

On the basis of the findings enumerated above, the following conclusions are generated:

1. The extent to which teachers practiced the following 21st century skills is high:
 - (a) Learning and Innovation Skills;
 - (b) Information, Media, and Digital Literacy Skills; and
 - (c) Life and Career Skills.
2. The Senior High School students' academic performance in the core subjects is generally in the outstanding level.
3. There is a significant and inverse relationship between the overall extent to which teachers practiced the 21st century skills and the students' performance in Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person.
4. There is a significant relationship between sex and the students' overall academic performance in the core subjects in favor of the female students. A significant relationship also existed between the type of Junior High School completed from and the students' overall academic performance in the core subjects in favor of those coming from public high schools.

In general, teachers' practices on the 21st century skills in their classroom instruction is High and the Senior High School students' academic performance is generally in the Outstanding level.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and the conclusions presented, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Foundation Preparatory Academy, Senior High School Department should create a Curriculum, Instruction, and Syllabi Committee to regularly revisit the course guides, curriculum content, teaching strategies, instructional resources, and assessment strategies, especially in Reading and Writing, 21st Century Literature, General Mathematics, and Introduction to Philosophy subjects, to assess the relevance of instructional practices to the changing times brought about by industrial revolution 4.0.
2. The Foundation Preparatory Academy administrators, after revisiting the curriculum, must initiate a move to invite experts from other schools who can conduct training for teachers and also share their best practices especially in the fields of Reading and Writing, 21st Century Literature, General Mathematics, and Introduction to Philosophy during in-service trainings and seminar workshops before the new agreed features of the curriculum can be implemented.

3. Foundation Preparatory Academy must include in the faculty development plan educational trips for teachers, especially in Reading and Writing, 21st Century Literature, General Mathematics, and Introduction to Philosophy teachers to benchmark other schools and adopt the practices best suited to the FPA school climate.
 4. Foundation Preparatory Academy must send teachers to seminars and conferences for teachers' up-skilling and reskilling through a transformed development program.
 5. Teachers' professional development for teaching core subjects using application of higher-order thinking skills and integration of technology must be emphasized.
 6. Future studies which will focus on the factors that affect the high performance of females than males must be conducted.
 7. Future studies in the teaching of Reading and Writing, 21st Century Literature, General Mathematics, and Introduction to Philosophy must be conducted to find out the underlying problems encountered by teachers and students in the enumerated subjects.
 8. Proposed activities in the action plan appended in this study must be considered for its implementation to enhance teachers' instructional strategies and skills in teaching students for a much improved academic performance.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher, being cautious with all of the prerequisites of ethical considerations, first asked for the permission from the Principal of the Foundation Preparatory Academy to consider the researcher's request for the Senior High School students' grades in their core subjects. Another letter request seeking permission for the researcher to do the data mining of the Senior High School graduates' grades in the registrar's office was given to the Dean of the University of Admission and Records together with the approved letter from the Principal of Foundation Preparatory Academy.

On the other hand, since a questionnaire was also used as another instrument in collecting the data on the students' perception of their teachers' extent of practice of the 21st century skills, the respondents of the study were informed via electronic mails and private messages sent via messenger about the purpose of the study and the significant contribution of the data to the researcher's endeavor. They were also informed that the information they revealed in their answers in the Google form will be treated with utmost confidentiality. In some cases like when they expressed doubts and second thoughts of not participating, their decisions were respected with tact by the researcher.

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